

Making Visible the Invisible: Experiences on Multidisciplinary Outdoors Groundwater Teaching at Bogotá Campus

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Abstract

Groundwater is a vital natural resource that brings over 50% of water supply systems and 45% of irrigation worldwide. However, like the well-known global pattern, groundwater still needs to be better understood and managed in Colombia, leaving several knowledge gaps among all stakeholders, from the citizens and the engineering and geosciences students and practitioners to the policy and decision-makers. In Bogotá, the country's capital, where the water supply comes predominantly from surface water, misconceptions and a mystic veil around groundwater prevail. This work presents the cooperation work performed by the Oficina de Gestión Ambiental of the Universidad Nacional de Colombia Sede Bogotá, together with engineering and sciences faculties through the last three years to project the value of the Bogotá Campus as an outdoors laboratory for teaching about groundwater to undergraduate and graduate level while information is gathered to support the campus management. Geosciences and engineering professors' wide range of interests in groundwater converge on the campus, where interdisciplinary practices that otherwise would take place in distant places, much of the time without the required conditions, can be held. Over the last three years, more than 100 undergraduate and graduate students have participated in groundwater-related activities, including water level measurement, hydraulic testing, physicochemical and isotopic sampling, and monitoring well construction. These practices let the students learn on and about the campus, making them conscious of the University's challenges and encouraging the development of new projects to resolve them while acquiring critical thinking. Finally, the work supports the University's goals in its Environmental Policy and changes the university decision-makers mindset about groundwater's potential for further campus development.

Keywords: Groundwater; Cooperation; Environmental Policy; Teaching and Research.

1 Introduction

Most of Earth's liquid freshwater is groundwater (about 98%) (but we don't "see" it); the rest is surface water (what we see) (UNESCO, 2022). This freshwater supports surface ecosystems (including humans and their needs). In the context of the current global water crisis, groundwater contributes to achieving 7 of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals –SDG– (The Groundwater Project, 2020) but for this to be a reality it is necessary to have adequate knowledge about it. In Colombia, 80% of the territory does not have sufficient studies on groundwater, and there are large gaps in the educational system in this regard.

Teaching about groundwater is a challenging task due to the invisible nature of subsurface processes and the problems in experiencing it directly, even in countries where this resource represents one of the most important sources of drinking water supply (Dickerson, Penick, Dawkins and Van Hoz, 2007). The interdisciplinary study of groundwater, hydrogeology, requires strong practical training to obtain reliable data in the field that will later be analyzed. Field practices have been identified as a valuable tool for groundwater education in a balanced and iterative cycle with theoretical and laboratory sessions (Gleeson, Allen and Ferguson, 2012). This practical training has the potential to significantly improve our understanding and management of groundwater, giving us hope for a more sustainable future.

The National University of Colombia is the country's main public university, with nine campuses throughout the country, with Bogotá being the largest. With more than 127 hectares, of which almost 75% is non-built area, the university city has 11 schools in all areas of knowledge, where environmental management is configured as a support for the management activities of the University and an articulator with academic activities. The Environmental Management Office (OGA) of the Bogotá Campus is a department attached to the vice-chancellor's office that aims to incorporate the Environmental dimension in the Campus processes, both in the fulfillment of its main activities as well as in the support and management, through actions of education, appropriation, prevention, mitigation, control and compensation of environmental aspects to comply with legal requirements within the framework of the SDG. It must ensure compliance with the University's environmental policy at the Bogotá Campus, from a perspective of University Environmental Responsibility, and of this with external actors.

Here we present our experiences of the last three years regarding the use of the Bogotá Campus as a practice center (Torres-Rojas & Ángel-Martínez, 2020) based on the cooperation established between the OGA, professors and students to promote active learning of hydrogeology in the fields of engineering and science.

Figure 1. Location map of the Bogotá Campus - University City of Bogotá and the groundwater monitoring network

2 Geologic and hydrogeologic context – Monitoring well network

The Bogotá Campus is located on the sediments originated by an ancient lake of Pleistocene age. The subsoil is composed of the intercalation of clays, silts and peat with minor beds of sand and gravel in the so-called Sabana Formation. Despite the prevalence of fine-grained sediments (aquitards) over coarse-grained sediments (aquifers), the Sabana Formation is considered a multilayer semi-confined aquifer. Despite the existence of more than 500 wells, dug wells and springs and their relevance to the industrial sector (Secretaría Distrital de Ambiente, 2023), knowledge about groundwater among the inhabitants of Bogotá is poor.

The OGA has established a groundwater monitoring network (Figure 1) composed of 29 monitoring points: a 275 m deep well and a 150 m deep piezometer, which provides information on the deepest part of the Sabana Formation and 27 monitoring wells ranging from 3 to 30 m deep, focusing mainly on the first 10 m of aquifers and aquitards on the Campus. The monitoring networks include both the existing infrastructures built by the Geological Service of Colombia and the university's Geotechnics laboratory. Recently, 8 new monitoring wells were built by the OGA to strengthen the monitoring network.

3 Methods

In a significant development in 2021, OGA procured state-of-the-art groundwater monitoring equipment and initiated strategic alliances with the Engineering and Science faculties. This collaboration aimed to gather data on the existing monitoring wells on Campus and historical groundwater level measurements conducted by student groups since 2016. Subsequently, systematic measurements of the water level were initiated. The historical and new data were then centralized in a geographic information system (GIS) database, which was made public, leading to data visualization through dashboards.

The cooperation scheme between OGA and teachers for improving outdoor groundwater teaching includes two educational contexts: in specific sessions of the classes (one or two per course) and in extra-curricular activities driven by the OGA or by student groups interested in deepening their groundwater knowledge. The first activity around groundwater between OGA and teachers took place at the end of 2021 with the leadership of the Geoscience Department, inviting the OGA as a guest to the first groundwater well inventory practice on campus carried out for the Hydrogeology class of the Geology undergraduate program. The practice used the existing monitoring network and the recently gathered information. This practice is now carried out semiannually. Then, due to the growing interest of Engineering teachers in using the Bogota Campus as an outdoor lab, a continuous wide range of activities was progressively added to groundwater-related classes of the civil engineering undergraduate program and the master in engineering (environmental and hydraulic resources), covering another groundwater point of view, including the study of i) the hydraulic properties of aquifers and aquitards by performing slug tests, ii) the physicochemical composition of groundwater by taking groundwater samples, analyzing it at the laboratory and interpreting the results and iii) the isotopic groundwater composition, by taking samples and shipping abroad for analysis to get insights regarding the contributing source (Bowen et al., 2019; Jasechko, 2019; Rozanski et al., 1993). Subsequently, in the last year (2023-2024), new practices designed for undergraduate and graduate subjects have been incorporated, where students participate directly by taking field data and then analyzing it (pump tests and slug tests).

Each outdoor practice begins with a brief introduction by OGA staff about the infrastructure that will be used in the practice and an update of the concepts seen in class by the teacher. The teacher and OGA's staff give some essential explanations about using the equipment and the procedures in the field and encourage the students to develop simple hands-on activities before carrying out the planned activity. The participating groups in the outdoor sessions commonly have at most 15 students, ensuring an engagement with the activities. Despite the particular nature of every class, the activities that take place in outdoor groundwater practices share the application of Cooperative-based learning techniques (Hernández-de-Menéndez, Vallejo Guevara, Tudón Martínez, Hernández Alcántara, & Morales-Menendez, 2019). For example, in Hydrogeology and Field Techniques classes practices, students form small groups and take the position of consultant firms or experts collecting information in the field, taking measurements and samples, and filling out the corresponding forms to later perform the corresponding analysis. During the practice, the teachers act as mentors, asking questions about the relevant topics of the practice, clarifying the students' doubts, and highlighting the key points.

In the analysis performed by students after the practices, several kinds of tools are used, for example, i) geologic to relate the subsurface materials with the groundwater flow and compositions, ii) hydrochemical to evaluate the interaction of groundwater with geological materials and how rainfall patterns affect the composition of the water, ii) isotopic, to analyze the hydrogen and oxygen isotopic abundance regarding the processes taking place during the water cycle at multiple scales (Bowen, Zhongyin, Fiorella, & Putman, 2019; Jasechko, 2019) and iii) hydraulic, to determine the geo-hidraulic parameters of the subsurface which controls the flow of groundwater.

Depending on the nature of the activities, students may generate new results, such as characteristic hydraulic values of aquifers or laboratory chemical tests. In such cases, the teacher, after conducting a quality control check, forwards the results to be uploaded to the OGA database. This establishes an iterative flow of information between the OGA and the students, bolstering the GIS database, which will serve as a valuable resource for future courses and research.

Figure 2. Conceptual model of the relationship between the OGA, teachers and students

Figure 3. Activities developed in the Bogota Campus. A) Students measuring the casing diameter of a well before take groundwater levels B) Monitoring well construction with the presence of geology and engineering students.

4 Results

Between July 2021 and April 2024, a total of 35 activities were developed at the Bogotá campus, with the participation of 247 students and five professors of engineering and sciences faculties. Considering that some could participate in more than one activity during this period, an estimated number of 225 benefited students

is assumed. Most of the activities, 60%, were held with the Engineering Faculty, 31% with Geosciences, and 9% in activities led by the OGA. Most students, 61%, were enrolled in engineering programs, including undergraduate and graduate levels, 36% with the geoscience undergraduate program, and 3% with other programs. The practices covered a wide range of topics around groundwater, with 51% related with purging, and considerations about physicochemical and isotopic sampling, 23% with field techniques used in the recognition and description of wells and monitoring wells and the measurement of water levels, 11% with hydraulic testing by conducting pumping test and slug test, including a successful 49-h pumping test in the campus well and 14% with diffusion of the state of art of groundwater in campus and demonstrations about the activities and process related with the construction of monitoring wells (Figure 3 B), an unique experience in the geologist and engineers education.

Figure 4. Cumulative number of students benefited between 2021 and 2024 differentiated by activities

Between 2021 and 2024 a total of 90 water samples were taken in the Bogota Campus, involving the hands-on experience of students in the process of purging, sampling and interpretation of the results. For 16% of the samples the students also participate performing the physicochemical analysis on the Environmental Engineering Laboratory of the University as part of the 2022 and 2023 Field Techniques classes. Figure 5 displays the graphic hydrochemical analysis perform to the dataset construct after the 2022 -2023 sampling campaigns using Piper and Gaillardet diagrams. These diagram are also examples of the free code interactive tools in Python available at the source code repository of the Environmental Hydrogeology class which can be access through the website: <https://binder.projectpythia.org/v2/gh/Peter24K2G/Curso.git/HEAD>. The results point out that the campus groundwater is bicarbonate between sodium – magnesian type (Figure 5b), with the presence of weathering of silicates such as montmorillonite. The piper diagram shows the water evolution from two end members: rain (TOT_HID) and the deepest aquifer tap by the Campus well [Piez_Ingeo], with mixing conditions for the shallow groundwater monitoring wells.

5 Discussion

As seen in Figure 4, the number of activities per year grew from 4 in 2021 to more than 17 in 2023, reflecting not only an increasing interest of professors in the use of the Campus for practices but also the number of students who have access to the unique groundwater physical spaces that the Bogota Campus offers an even participates on the groundwater monitoring network expansion recently made. In the outdoor practices

described, a student-centered learning approach is applied. The solid hands-on component, which includes the wide range of aspects described around groundwater, linked with real-life situations faced by hydrogeologists and environmental sciences in field activities, engages the students and motivates them with the classes in a way that could not be achieved in a passive learning method.

The activities performed at the outdoor practices go beyond taking measurements and taking samples. For example, in the Field Techniques class, the professor promotes cooperative learning techniques in which the student works together and understands team dynamics, focusing on social skills such as leadership, communication, and conflict management (Gleason et al., 2011) required to perform the proposed task.

Figure 5. Hydrochemical analysis of groundwater in Bogota Campus. a) Source Code repository outline for graphic hydrochemical analysis <https://binder.projectpythia.org/v2/gh/Peter24K2G/Curso.git/HEAD>, b) Piper diagram of march 2023 samples showing the major ion water composition evolution c) Stiff diagram of the Campus well showing a bicarbonate sodium/magnesium water type, D) Gaillardet diagram showing the groundwater interaction with the aquifer, mainly silicate weathering.

The students faced not just planning a campaign, performing the proper purge (often overlooked by consultants), taking the sample, filling the corresponding forms, preserving the samples ultimately, and performing the dissolved species determination in the Environmental Engineering Laboratory of the University, using the proper standards (APHA, AWWA, & WEF, 2017). In the whole process, they deal with logistic matters, which often affect timetable fulfillment in many real-time sampling campaigns, improving the development of competencies such as collaboration, autonomy, logic, creative thinking, and problem-solving, added value of

active learning pedagogical strategies (Hernández-de-Menéndez et al., 2019). The next step, after the sample analysis is available, is ease because of the acquired knowledge during the practices about the hydrogeologic setting. The flexibility that free code interactive tools in Python offer (see Figure 5) enhances the simultaneous visualization of an increasing dataset, letting the student identify trends and derive meaningful conclusions.

The learning goals converge despite the outdoor sessions, including geoscience and engineering perspectives. For example, after the practices, the students should be able to identify the differences between monitoring and groundwater wells, know how to properly take groundwater level measurements, and choose the appropriate procedure to take representative groundwater samples for physicochemical and isotopic analyses.

Finally, the information gathered during the outdoor practices contributes to progressively strengthening the OGA's hydrogeology GIS dataset, giving more tools to the next students participating in the Campus practices.

6 Next steps

Despite the progress gained during the last three years and the increasing interest of engineering and science teachers applying the active learning approach in the University City around groundwater, the next steps will be focused on tracking and evaluating the impact that the performed activities have on the level of student's conceptualization of hydrogeology and groundwater to improve the activities. The projected approach will include applying surveys on students attending future activities and former students. The outdoor practices, in conjunction with related concept tests, will also be used to assess students' comprehension of topics covered in the practices before or after class. Meanwhile, groundwater information will be gathered to enhance the available dataset for teaching and increase the insight of groundwater flow and composition in the Bogota Campus, supporting the OGA activities.

The growing information available for students, professors, and University decision-makers and the engagement established between these stakeholders eventually led to the retooling of the Bogota campus from a passive to an active environment for teaching and learning, establishing a living lab framework in a co-creative ecosystem, like the University of Manchester experience (Evans, Jones, Karvonen, Millard, & Wendler, 2015).

7 Conclusions

Between 2021 and 2024, 225 students of engineering and geoscience programs at undergraduate and graduate levels by the application took part in outdoor practices in the Bogota Campus of the Universidad Nacional de Colombia due to the cooperation between the Oficina de Gestion Ambiental and professors. This approach led the students to strengthen their knowledge by interacting directly with the groundwater campus, in cooperative based learning practices including water sampling, hydraulic test, and groundwater well inventory.

These practices that can be carried out in the campus infrastructure itself constitute an excellent advantage for the university, undergraduate, and graduate students (Science and Engineering). The respective professors facilitate learning through the direct and appropriate execution of field techniques (best practices through direct use of equipment and methods) and simultaneously allow significant progress in the detailed knowledge of the characteristics of groundwater in the subsoil of this sector of Bogotá, progressively also becoming a pilot laboratory for the advancement of the local hydrogeological knowledge, with country-scale projections for the training of hydrogeology professionals who contribute to closing the knowledge gap in the territory of Colombia..

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